

HONEYCOMB CORES WITH A NEGATIVE POISSON'S RATIO FOR USE IN COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

Honeycomb cores for use in sandwich panels are generally made with a hexagonal cell structure, which leads to anticlastic curvatures when the cores are bent. The much more useful synclastic curvature condition can be achieved by making cores that exhibit a negative Poisson's ratio. This is possible if the honeycomb is made with a re-entrant cell geometry, such as a dovetail pattern. The orthogonal curvatures of conventional and re-entrant networks are entirely determined by the two in-plane Poisson's ratios and can be predicted from the geometrical parameters of the cells. By measuring the curvature ratios of honeycomb sheets it is possible to determine the two Poisson's ratios. Measurements have been made on aluminium and unstiffened cardboard honeycombs. The relatively stiff aluminium honeycombs can be predictably deformed on bending to form double curvatures. Cardboard honeycombs with negative Poisson's ratios exhibit a much higher degree of drapeability and are suitable for deforming to much more complex doubly curved surfaces.

KEYWORDS: Honeycombs; Cores; Sandwich panels; Negative Poisson's ratio.

1.INTRODUCTION

It has been demonstrated by, inter alia, R.Lakes (1) and L.J.Gibson, M.F.Ashby et al (2),(3) how three-dimensional and two-dimensional cellular structures can be transformed into re-entrant forms which feature a negative Poisson's ratio. In this paper we consider the consequences of a negative Poisson's ratio on the flexure properties of the two-dimensional cellular honeycombs used as core materials in the fabrication of sandwich panels. Such sandwich panels, fabricated from relatively thin flat sheets separated by a lightweight honeycomb core, have found wide application because of the very high specific flexural modulus that the structure possesses. Flat panels of this type are easily made by glueing fibre-reinforced epoxy or polyester sheets on to the faces of aluminium or stiffened paper honeycombs, which are relatively easy to make with a hexagonal cell structure. However, a hexagonal honeycomb core of finite thickness, in common with almost all conventional materials, exhibits a positive Poisson's ratio. This effective Poisson's ratio is due to the geometry of the honeycombs and has little to do with the Poisson's ratio of the material forming the core (2)- (4). An important

consequence of this is that bending the core to form a curved surface induces an anticlastic curvature orthogonal to the primary curvature, creating a saddle shape. Thus, in fabricating sandwich panels from cores with a hexagonal cell structure there is a problem in that the core will not drape naturally to conform with the synclastic curvatures characteristic of many common components, such as car doors, boat hulls etc.. This problem can be overcome by transforming the network to a re-entrant, i.e dovetail, form, so that the Poisson's ratio becomes negative. It has been shown theoretically (4) that a core with this configuration must deform with synclastic curvatures on bending and that this effect is entirely due to the negative Poisson's ratio.

A model of the effects of geometry on the tensile and compressive properties of honeycombs has been proposed (2), which assumes that the principal mode of cell deformation at small strains is due to beam flexure. Using this model an analysis of the deformation of regular networks has shown that the specific mechanical properties depend only on cell shape and not on cell size. The analysis provides quantitative predictions of the moduli, Poisson ratios and densities of the networks. The veracity of these predictions has been confirmed by the experimental measurements of Gibson et al (2) on rubber honeycombs and on commercially available aluminium honeycombs. This model has been used (4) to predict the orthogonal curvatures that develop when a two-dimensional network is bent. The present paper presents experimental results for honeycombs made from two materials, with varying hexagonal and re-entrant geometries, to provide a comparison with the Poisson's ratios predicted by the model.

2. THEORY

Sandwich panels are typically fabricated by firmly attaching a pair of relatively thin skins or plates to a lightweight cellular core. It is well established that the excellent specific flexural modulus of these structures is due to the large second moment of area of the panel. Prior to the attachment of the skins the core can exhibit low or very low in-plane moduli. The high flexural modulus of the panel is only achieved when the effects of the intrinsically low in-plane moduli of the core are suppressed by the presence of the skins. In examining the effects of cell shape on Poisson's ratio and in-plane modulus it is convenient to define the parameters of a typical honeycomb in terms of a regular hexagonal cell as shown in Figure 1. A re-entrant cell is defined as one in which θ has a negative value.

The relatively low in-plane moduli of the core can be an advantage in that, in principle, the core can be shaped by bending before the skins are attached. In order to bend a plate it is necessary to apply a moment along the side of the plate (4), parallel for example to the 2 axis. This induces a curvature with radius R_1 . A secondary curvature R_2 , orthogonal to R_1 , is also induced that is solely due to the Poisson contraction along the 2 axis, such that :

$$R_2 = -R_1/\nu_{12} \quad [1]$$

Thus, if ν_{12} is positive the double curvature is anticlastic, but if ν_{12} can be made negative a more useful synclastic curvature is produced.

A more detailed analysis of plate deformation in flexure has been developed by Evans (4) which assumes that the radii in equation 1 will approximate to circles at small strains. At larger deformations the radii of curvature away from the central region of the plate are parabolic. However, even for large deformations the radii of curvature near to the centre of the plate will be approximated by some average curvatures R_1 and R_2 , related as in equation 1. Thus the measurement of R_1 and R_2 at low deflections offers a route to the measurement of ν_{12} and ν_{21} for a plate specimen of a honeycomb core.

FIGURE 1. DEFINITION OF CELL PARAMETERS.

The equations relating the geometrical parameters of the cell, defined in Figure 1, to the moduli and Poisson's ratios of two-dimensional cellular structures are also quoted by Evans (3) and are based on the beam flexure model of Gibson, et al. (2). The equations of interest in the present work concern the prediction of the two Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{21} and the moduli E_1 and E_2 . The equations are :

$$E_1 = E_s \left(\frac{t}{l}\right)^3 \left[\frac{\alpha + \sin \theta}{\cos^3 \theta} \right] \quad [2]$$

$$E_2 = E_s \left(\frac{t}{l}\right)^3 \left[\frac{\cos \theta}{(\alpha + \sin \theta) \sin^2 \theta} \right] \quad [3]$$

$$\nu_{12} = \frac{\sin \theta}{\cos^2 \theta} [\alpha + \sin \theta] \quad [4]$$

$$\nu_{21} = \frac{\cos^2 \theta}{\sin \theta} \left[\frac{1}{\alpha + \sin \theta} \right] \quad [5]$$

where h , l , and t are defined in Figure 1 and $\alpha = h / l$. E_s is the intrinsic modulus of the cell-wall material. These equations show that the Poisson's ratio is independent of the cell size and only depends on $\alpha = (h/l)$ and θ . In marked contrast with this is the strong dependence of the moduli on cell size, because of the term $1/l^3$ in the governing equations.

A commonly used honeycomb core material is aluminium and Gibson et al (2) have shown that the mechanical properties of hexagonal aluminium honeycombs give a good fit to the predictions based on the flexure model. A rather different type of honeycomb core is that made from resin-impregnated cardboard or paper. Cardboard honeycombs of this type, particularly if they are not resin-stiffened, feature much lower in-plane moduli than aluminium honeycombs, and do not deform elastically in that they do not spontaneously recover their original dimensions after they have been strained. Observation of the deformation mode of unstiffened cardboard honeycombs suggests that during extension or compression both beam flexing and cell joint hinging may occur concurrently. For a

perfect frictionless hinge the moduli would be zero, but of course this condition is not realised in practice. For hinged structures subjected to moderate or gross deformation it is suggested that the change in Poisson's ratio is entirely due to the change in the angle θ associated with the hinging. In the flexure model the effect of straining the network by a small amount does not change θ significantly. In both models, however, the Poisson's ratio at a given strain state is only dependent on θ and α . The same governing equations can thus be used to predict the Poisson's ratios of both types of network.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

The primary aim of the present work were (a) to develop a method for determining the Poisson's ratio of honeycomb sheets by measuring the ratio of the two orthogonal curvatures obtained by flexing the sheets, (b) to obtain similar data from tensile or compressive tests on specimens with appropriate aspect ratios, and (c) to compare these two sets of values with data obtained by prediction from the beam flexure model.

3.1 Materials Experiments were made with two types of honeycomb, made from aluminium and unstiffened cardboard. The aluminium networks were commercial Aeroweb hexagonal honeycombs (provided by Ciba-Geigy) and featured a range of cell sizes. With one of these networks the cell size ($h = 10\text{mm}$, $l = 12\text{mm}$, $\theta = 35^\circ$) was sufficiently large for it to be possible to transform this to a re-entrant configuration by carefully bending the appropriate sides of the hexagons inwards for each individual cell.

The cardboard networks were constructed by hand by folding sheets of card to form a box-pleated structure. By glueing these box-pleated sheets together it was possible to make both the conventional hexagonal honeycombs and the re-entrant versions.

3.2 Poisson's ratio measurements The experimental programme was designed to provide results from two types of specimen :

(a) Flat honeycomb sheets, which were used to characterise the synclastic and anticlastic curvature ratios when the sheets were bent. These ratios represent the two orthogonal Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{21} .

(b) Long specimens with an aspect ratio large enough to eliminate end effects during the direct measurement of ν_{12} and ν_{21} in tensile and compressive tests.

In preliminary tests it was found that tensile and compressive tests on the square sheets did not give the correct values for ν_{12} and ν_{21} . This was because the shape of the specimen inhibited the longitudinal extension of the material and led to high estimates of ν . Ideally, an aspect ratio of at least 5 : 1 is needed to avoid end effects in the direct measurement of ν in tensile or compression tests.

3.3 Curvature measurements The curvature measurements were made by bolting two rods to the opposite edges of the approximately square sheet specimens. These rods were used to apply the primary bending moment to the sheet, thus creating the primary curvature R_1 and the orthogonal secondary curvature R_2 . The rods were clamped to hold the configuration constant and the curvatures were measured by a photographic method, using a camera with a fixed focal length to maintain a constant magnification. The camera tripod was fitted with a rail system to facilitate focusing without altering the focal length of the camera lens. With the anticlastically curved panels a fine thread was strung across the centre of curved specimen to enable the focus to be sharp at the plane of

primary or secondary curvature. With the synclastically curved specimens the thread was draped along these planes to follow the convex contours of the deformed panel. Figure 2 shows a photograph of the primary and secondary curvatures of an anticlastically curved panel with the thread marking the focusing planes.

The photographic negatives were mounted in transparency frames and a conventional projector was used to form an enlarged image of each curvature on a large sheet of paper. The enlarged curvature profile was traced onto the paper for measurement. Care was taken to ensure that all these tracings were made at the same degree of enlargement. From the profiles measurements were made of the arc heights (BD) at various chord lengths (AC). From these measurements the curvature was calculated using the equations :

$$\beta = \tan^{-1} BD / 0.5AC \quad [6]$$

$$R = 0.5BD / \sin^2 \beta \quad [7]$$

For each panel measurements were made over a wide range of primary curvatures. Using the rods to flex the honeycombs it is possible to induce both positive primary or negative primary curvatures. Positive and negative curvatures are defined in Figure 2. As indicated in the theory section of the paper the curvature ratio method gives the best estimate of ν when the curvature approaches zero. Accordingly a plot was made of the reciprocals of the curvatures in the 1 and 2 directions. Provided that data has been obtained with both positive and negative primary curvatures equation [1] predicts that a straight line plot should result, passing through zero, with a slope $1 / \nu$.

For each honeycomb specimen two sets of measurements can be made, with the rods attached to the two pairs of specimen edges, such that both ν_{12} and ν_{21} can be estimated. To illustrate the method the plot for one of the aluminium honeycombs is shown in Figure 3. With the aluminium specimens the intrinsic rigidity of the honeycombs was sufficiently high to render gravity effects on the specimens insignificant and the measurements were the same with the honeycomb mounted either horizontally, with positive or negative curvatures, or vertically. This was not the case with the cardboard specimens, which showed considerable variations in curvature when a horizontal flexed specimen was inverted. To minimise this effect, therefore, all the curvature measurements with the cardboard specimens were made with the specimen mounted vertically and with the primary curvature generated about the horizontal axis.

3.4 Direct tensile or compression measurements. For the direct measurement of the Poisson's ratio from tensile tests the specimens were subjected to a series of different longitudinal strains by either attaching weights to a suspended specimen or by clamping the specimen ends whilst the specimen lay flat on a table. Length and width measurements for longitudinal and transverse gauge lengths away from the ends of the specimens were made with a lens and a ruler. By making a series of measurements at increasing longitudinal strains, up to a maximum Engineering strain of about 0.03, it was found that a plot of ϵ_t vs ϵ_l was sufficiently linear for ν to be determined from the slope of this plot. At these relatively low strains no difference was detected in the ν values determined by tension or compression. Some modulus measurements were made on some of the networks, and it was noted that at small strains the compressive and tensile Young's moduli were the same. In the present investigation the main focus of interest was in measuring the Poisson's ratios and it was sufficient to compare the order of magnitude of the moduli of the aluminium and cardboard networks.

FIGURE 2. PHOTOGRAPHS OF DEFORMED NETWORKS.

Examples of (a) positively, (b) negatively curved honeycombs with anticlastic curvatures and (c) a synclastically curved re-entrant honeycomb.

(a) positively curved hexagonal honeycomb

(b) positively curved hexagonal honeycomb showing negative secondary curvature

(c) synclastically curved re-entrant honeycomb

Figure 3. Reciprocal curvature data from hexagonal aluminium honeycomb H7.

4. RESULTS

Honeycombs made from both aluminium and cardboard were used for the experiments which featured both conventional hexagonal cells and re-entrant hexagonal cells. Cell shape and cell size were both varied in order to provide a good comparison between the predicted and measured values. In defining the geometrical parameters of the cell, as specified in Figure 2, it is necessary to measure h and l , which provide the ratio α . A good way of obtaining the angle θ is then to obtain an accurate estimate of the cell width, w , since $\cos^{-1}\theta$ is given by $0.5w/l$.

Table 1 below summarises the results obtained on a range of honeycombs. The geometrical parameters of each honeycomb are listed, together with the predicted and measured Poisson's ratios.

Because of the difficulty in making suitable specimens full data are not available for all the geometries considered. It is also the case that the cell wall lengths of conventional aluminium honeycombs are not ideal for converting into the re-entrant versions because they yield extremely anisotropic networks. However, the results obtained with both the aluminium and cardboard networks are sufficiently comprehensive to show the underlying trends. With some of the networks it was not found possible to exactly match the geometries of the curvature and tensile specimens. In such cases both geometries are quoted and predictions based on equations [4] and [5] are given for each case. There were also some difficulties in obtaining two orthogonal specimens with a sufficiently high aspect ratio to be able to measure both ν_{12} and ν_{21} by the direct method. In such cases the second value has been taken as the reciprocal of the measured value (see below for reasoning) and is included in parentheses in the Table.

Table 1. Predicted and measured Poisson's ratios.

<u>Network</u>	<u>Cell parameters</u>			<u>Theoretical</u>		<u>Tensile</u>		<u>Curvature</u>	
	θ°	h	l	ν_{12}	ν_{21}	ν_{12}	ν_{21}	ν_{12}	ν_{21}
H2 hexagonal cardboard	44.5	10	8	2.71	0.37			2.0	0.29
H4 hexagonal cardboard	45.3	9	8	2.64	0.38	2.57	0.38		
H6 hexagonal aluminium	38.0	10	10	1.60	0.62	1.85	0.59	1.85	(.54)
H7 hexagonal aluminium	40.1	3.1	4.2	1.52	0.69	1.32	(0.76)	1.50	0.67
H20 hexagonal aluminium	40.1	6.3	8.35	1.54	0.65			1.54	0.65
R20 re-entrant aluminium	35.4	9.8	12.26	1.20	0.83	1.22	(0.82)	1.10	0.80
R2 re-entrant cardboard	-11.5	9.5	12.5	-0.12	-8.61			-0.1	-6.5
	-8.1	14.5	18.7	-0.01	-10.96	-0.05	-10.57		
	-42	15	8	-1.45	-0.68	-1.42	(-0.70)	-1.0	-0.30

5. DISCUSSION

The results in Table 1. show that with the aluminium honeycombs very reasonable agreement between the predicted and measured ν values has been obtained . The extreme case is the highly anisotropic network R20. The two examples of this re-entrant network that were available for direct measurement and for curvature measurement were not identical in θ and gave rather different predicted values for the two ν values. Within this range of α and θ values ν_{21} is extremely sensitive to very small changes in θ and because of the relatively crude way in which these networks were prepared there was significant variation in the individual θ values for the cells within each network. In these circumstances the level of agreement achieved from both the direct and curvature measurements with the predicted values for these networks is considered to be satisfactory.

The results show that for these aluminium honeycombs the curvature ratio method is a useful method for the measurement of ν . Most importantly they show the possibility of designing honeycomb cores with a natural tendency to drape to form any given double curvature. Quite complex shapes could, in principle, be obtained by varying the cell shape within a honeycomb core. From the standpoint of formability, cores made from re-entrant cells are potentially more useful than conventional hexagonal cores, because of the wide range of common objects and structures that have synclastic curvatures. For the reasons detailed earlier the formability is lost when the composite sandwich panel is completed by attaching the outer skins, to produce a very rigid structure.

With the unstiffened cardboard networks the results show that the tensile test measurements of Poisson's ratio agree well with the values predicted by the governing equations. With the curvature measurements, however, there is clear evidence of a divergence between the predicted and measured values. It should be noted that the dominant deformation mode when these networks are strained is that of cell joint hinging, for which the flexure model does not provide a description. In

general, for elastic materials, the symmetry of the stiffness matrix requires :

$$v_{21}E_1 = v_{12}E_2 \quad [8]$$

In the original model for two-dimensional foams, based on beam wall flexure, it was found (2) that this expression reduced to the special case of :

$$v_{21} = (v_{12})^{-1} \quad [9]$$

The accuracy of this expression is then a measure of the accuracy of the model. Deviations from this result can be due either to deformation modes other than flexure (for example stretching or hinging) or to inelastic (e.g. plastic) deformation. As noted above the values in parentheses in Table 1 were obtained from equation [9].

Although the cardboard networks did not conform with the theoretical predictions, they did show considerable formability, particularly with the re-entrant versions. This is particularly noticeable with the network R2, which has v_{12} and v_{21} approaching -1. Theoretically an isotropic network with $v = -1$ would give the maximum formability for curvature in two directions and would be expected to be capable of conforming to the surface of a sphere. At the other extreme a honeycomb with cells with $\theta = 0$ would only be expected to form a single curvature.

Thus, the stiffer aluminium cores can be designed to deform predictably to a given double curvature, whilst the re-entrant cardboard networks are well suited to deforming to more complex doubly curved surfaces, particularly when the Poisson's ratios are close to -1.

6. CONCLUSIONS

1. Honeycombs made with re-entrant, or dovetail, cells exhibit negative Poisson's ratios. When flexed the honeycombs form into a dome shape, i.e. they curve synclastically. This effect is entirely due to the negative Poisson's ratios and the associated curvatures can be predicted from the two Poisson's ratios. Similarly, the anticlastic curvatures associated with conventional hexagonal honeycombs can be predicted from the Poisson's ratios.
2. A method for the determination of the Poisson's ratios of two-dimensional hexagonal and re-entrant networks from the measurement of these curvatures has been developed.
3. With relatively stiff networks, made from aluminium, the Poisson's ratios measured by this method agree well with data obtained directly from tensile or compression measurements and with predictions based on the beam flexure model of Gibson et al. (2).
4. With cardboard networks the measured Poisson's ratios agree less well with predictions made by the governing equations, principally due to their large strain deformation.
5. Honeycombs with re-entrant cells offer attractive possibilities for the fabrication of curved composite sandwich panels. Aluminium cores may be designed with either a constant or a varying re-entrant cell geometry to fashion a core that deforms predictably to a variety of given synclastic curvatures. The cardboard cores are capable of very high drapeability, especially when both the v values = -1.

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